

Mortality of BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* due to treatments with increasing doses of germinated (germ.) and nongerminated (not germ.) *B. bassiana* conidia, IRRI, 1988. In one treatment (hum.), cages were incubated at 100% relative humidity before transfer to the greenhouse.

1 g/ 100 ml was added to 50% of the suspension (dextrose stimulates conidia germination). The dextrose suspension

was incubated at 25 °C; the suspension without dextrose, at 15 °C for 10 h. More than 90% of the conidia with dextrose and less than 5% of the conidia without dextrose germinated. Serial dilutions of 10², 10³, 10⁵, and 10⁷ conidia/ ml of both suspensions were prepared.

To test infection, 50 adult alate BPH were used per treatment. Insects were dipped in the conidia solution for about 60 s and transferred to filter paper to drain. Control insects were dipped in Tween 80 solution. Insects were incubated on potted rice plants in mylar cages. Half the cages were covered with plastic bags for 2.5 h immediately after

fungi application to raise RH to saturation. All pots were kept in a greenhouse at 25-30 °C (day) and 15-20 °C (night) for 5 d. Live and infected (dead and fungi-covered) insects were counted. Mortality due to fungus infection was calculated as

$$\text{mortality (\%)} = 100\% \times \frac{\text{no. infected insects}}{\text{no. infected insects} + \text{no. living insects}}$$

The results (see figure) show lessening, but not significantly different mortality with increasing fungus conidia treatment. Pregermination of the fungus *B. hassiana* conidia and 2 h incubation at saturated RH did not increase BPH infection. □

Managing other pests

Weaverbirds, pests of rice in Badeggi, Niger State, Nigeria

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Weaverbirds in ricefields, Badeggi, Nigeria, 1983-84.

We surveyed weaverbird infestation Jun 1983-May 1984 in Badeggi ricefields (9°45'N, 6°7'E). (Rice in this locality is an irrigated crop on a floodplain referred to as the "Fadama.")

Mist nets were used to trap birds for 2

wk every month. Eleven species caused varying degrees of damage to rice (see table). Yield loss on some randomly selected fields ranged from 0.7 to 23.2%. □

Species	Food habits	Damage		Pest status	Relative occurrence (%)
		Crop stage	Severity		
Red-headed quelea <i>Quelea erythrops</i> (Hartlaub)	Picking, consumption of maturing and ripe grains	Sowing-late maturity	Severe	Major	70
Village weaverbird <i>Ploceus cucullatus</i> (Muller)	Picking, consumption of maturing and ripe grains	Sowing-late maturity	Severe	Major	70
Black-headed weaver <i>Ploceus melanocephalus</i> (L)	Picking, consumption of maturing and ripe grains	Sowing-late maturity	Severe	Major	90
Bush sparrow <i>Petronia</i> sp.	Picking, consumption of maturing and ripe grains	Sowing-late maturity	Moderately severe	Minor	5-10
Grey-headed sparrow <i>Passer griseus</i> (Vieillot)	Picking, consumption of maturing and ripe grains	Sowing-late maturity	Moderately severe	Minor	40-50
Yellow crowned bishop <i>Euplectes afer</i> (Gmelin)	Puncturing and consumption of maturing and ripe grains	Milky-maturing	Moderately severe	Minor	40-50
Red bishop <i>Euplectes orix</i> (L)	Puncturing and consumption of maturing and ripe grains	Milky-maturing	Moderately severe	Minor	40-50
Bronze manikin <i>Lonchura cucullatus</i> (Swainson)	Puncturing and sucking	Milky early dough	Moderately severe	Minor	40-50
Senegal fire-finch <i>Lagonosticta senegala</i> (L)	Puncturing and sucking	Milky early dough	Moderately severe	Minor	5-10
Black-rumped waxbill <i>Estrilda troglodytes</i> (Lichtenstein)	Puncturing and sucking	Milky early dough	Moderately severe	Minor	5-10
Zebra waxbill <i>Amndava subflava</i> (Vieillot)	Puncturing and sucking	Milky early dough	Moderately severe	Minor	5-10